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ENGLISH LANGUAGE SPEAKING ANXIETY AMONG GRADE 10 STUDENTS AT ARCELO MEMORIAL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the English language speaking anxiety levels of students in Arcelo Memorial National High School. The significant relationship between the English language speaking anxiety and the students' academic performance were also taken. The study was conducted at Arcelo Memorial National High School during the School Year 2023-2024. A correlational research design was used in gathering and treatment of data and an adapted survey questionnaire was used to complete the gathering of student's emotional and social anxiety experiences in the classroom. The respondents were randomly selected through cluster random sampling. Findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between the student's heightened anxiety to their low academic performance in the English subject. Participants also showed high numbers of "agree" in the emotional and social factors of speaking anxiety. Based on the findings and conclusion, it is highly recommended to utilize effective strategies to mitigate the English language speaking anxiety among students.

Keywords: Relationship, English Language Speaking Anxiety, Academic Performance, Grade 10 students, Emotional and Social Factors, Coping Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Many students, particularly non-native English speakers, have struggled with public speaking due to the complexities of the English language. English is a universal language, but its complicated grammar rules, extensive vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and varying accents have made it a challenging language to master. This complexity often leads to speaking anxiety, a common issue in social or academic settings. Speaking anxiety refers to feelings of unease, fear, or nervousness in situations where individuals are required to speak a language, they are not confident in. It is often triggered by a fear of making mistakes, being judged, or misunderstood, which can hinder students' participation in public speaking or class discussions (Llera & Newman, 2020; Palupi, 2021). When a person is in public, speaking anxiety is an unpleasant scenario for him or her (Syahfutra, 2021).

In the Philippines, where English is used as a second language and is crucial for academic success, speaking anxiety is a challenge for many students. During English classes, active participation is necessary for improving communication skills, but many students avoid speaking tasks due to anxiety. This reluctance can negatively affect their academic performance and overall confidence. Addressing this anxiety is essential to creating a

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supportive environment where students can engage more fully, allowing them to enhance both their language proficiency and academic performance.

The researchers in this study, motivated by their personal experiences with speaking anxiety, sought to explore the issue further. During their early years in the English program, they faced anxiety when participating in discussions or presentations, mainly due to the fear of being judged by their peers. Over time, through continuous practice and exposure, their confidence increased, but traces of anxiety remained. This personal journey led the researchers to conduct a study on the speaking anxiety among Grade 10 students at Arcelo Memorial National High School. They aimed to investigate the relationship between students' speaking anxiety and their academic performance in English.

The study anchored its findings in several well-established theories. Albert Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory offered insights into how students with high self-efficacy approached speaking tasks with confidence, setting challenging goals and demonstrating resilience. In contrast, students with low self-efficacy tended to avoid speaking tasks, perceiving them as too difficult. Stephen Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis explained how emotional factors, such as anxiety, raised an internal barrier that hindered language acquisition. When anxiety was high, the affective filter blocked the students' ability to learn and practice effectively. Lastly, Gardner's Socio-Educational Model emphasized the role of cultural and social influences on students' anxiety levels, including peer relationships, teacher interactions, and classroom environment. Understanding these influences helped the researchers develop a framework for creating supportive interventions aimed at reducing speaking anxiety and improving academic outcomes.

This study aimed to identify key factors that hinder academic success. Understanding this relationship can help in creating targeted interventions to support students, reduce their anxiety, and enhance their overall academic performance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used a correlation research design which focuses on the English language speaking anxiety among Grade 10 students using survey questionnaires as a measurement tool and the collection of their academic performance.

The study employed the Input-Process-Output Model. In this study, the input consists of variables related to the speaking anxiety factors such as the emotional and social aspects and the academic performances of Grade 10 students during the third quarter of school year 2023-2024. Additionally, the study explored the relationship between academic performance and their overall English speaking anxiety levels.

The process involved the treatment of data using descriptive statistics, including the weighted mean and percentage and utilized the use of Correlational statistics of Pearson Correlation Coefficient in determining the relationship of the variables. The data gathered were processed. There was analysis and interpretation of data obtained.

The findings of the study entail the usage of the output which is the development of an action plan on effective strategies to cope English speaking anxiety.

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The research was conducted at Arcelo Memorial National High School, is a secondary public school situated in the Barangay of San Vicente, Lilo-an, Cebu established in 1978.

The respondents of the study were the Grade 10 students of Arcelo Memorial National High School – Day Class for the school year 2023-2024. Out of twenty (20) Grade 10 sections, one (1) section has been randomly selected using cluster sampling. The section has a total number of 50 students who were then selected as respondents.

The questionnaire that was utilized in this study was an adapted survey questionnaire developed by MacIntyre (2014) which was a 4-point Likert Scale called the Shortened-Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (S-FLCAS). The survey questionnaire assessed the level of speaking anxiety experienced by individuals especially when speaking in a foreign language in the classroom. The content variable consists of ten (10) questions. This survey questionnaire may include close-ended questions for participants to indicate the frequency of the factors of their anxiety.

Before the researchers administered the survey questionnaires, the researchers sought the recommending approval of the Dean of Instruction at Cebu Technological University-Consolacion Campus and the School Head of Arcelo Memorial National High School. Upon approval, they randomly selected a Grade 10 section for the study. They then briefed the Grade 10 teacher of the selected section with an approved letter explaining the study's purpose and importance. With the teachers' consent, the researchers distributed the online survey link to the students via the teacher in their group chat. After collecting the completed surveys, the gathered data underwent descriptive analysis to summarize its characteristics. Additionally, correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between language speaking anxiety and academic performance.

To determine the average anxiety levels reported by respondents and the variation in their responses across various items based on the 4-point Likert scale and to calculate the average of the grades acquired, weighted mean and percentage was used. Pearson's Correlation Coefficient was used to determine if an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in the other.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to assess the English language speaking anxiety among Grade 10 students at Arcelo Memorial National High School, with the goal of implementing strategies to help alleviate anxiety related to speaking in English. There were 981 total number of Grade 10 students enrolled in the school, and the study utilized a correlational method with a focused sample of 50 participants.

To measure academic performance, the researchers collected the respondents' third-quarter grades in English for the School Year 2023-2024. The results were summarized using frequencies and percentages, and the students' performance was categorized into three levels: below average, average, and

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above average. The majority of the students were classified as "average," indicating that they had satisfactory performance in their English class during the third quarter.

The emotional and social factors contributing to English language speaking anxiety were examined through a 4-point Likert-type survey questionnaire. The responses were processed using weighted mean calculations.

The findings indicated that English language speaking anxiety among Grade 10 students varied based on emotional and social factors. Specifically, students reported significant anxiety when required to speak without preparation, with a weighted mean of 3.17 for emotional factors. This suggests that unprepared speaking tasks induce considerable stress, emphasizing the need for supportive teaching strategies to reduce anxiety. Social factors also played a role, with a weighted mean of 3.24, highlighting that the presence of an audience, particularly teachers and classmates, heightened anxiety. This underscores the importance of creating a supportive and non-judgmental classroom environment to reduce pressure and foster student confidence.

The relationship between the students' academic performance and their anxiety levels was analyzed using Pearson's Correlation Coefficient. The results revealed a strongly significant negative correlation, indicating that higher levels of speaking anxiety were strongly associated with lower academic performance in English.

Based on the findings, students grappling with English language speaking anxiety can adopt various coping strategies to alleviate their stress levels. For students, diligent preparation for speaking tasks can diminish panic and anxiety, and incorporating mindfulness techniques such as deep breathing exercises or visualization practices, can aid students in managing their anxiety levels effectively. Moreover, teachers could elevate the student's anxiety through the implementation of supportive teaching methods, which offer encouragement and assistance, and can cultivate a nurturing learning environment conducive to anxiety reduction. Additionally, fostering a non-judgmental atmosphere in the classroom, where students feel free from scrutiny and pressure, is crucial in assuaging anxiety related to speaking tasks.

CONCLUSION

The study explored the emotional and social factors influencing the English language speaking anxiety among Grade 10 students and its relationship to their academic performance in the English subject. The study found a significant negative correlation between anxiety and academic performance, highlighting the impact of high level of anxiety on students' low educational outcomes.

The study concludes that implementing an action plan with strategies to cope with English language speaking anxiety in the classroom is highly effective in addressing anxiety and enhancing students' academic performance.

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